

CoARA WG TIER – Towards an Inclusive Evaluation of Research

WG (Co-)Chairs:

Silvia Penati (Chair), Bonaria Biancu (Deputy Chair), Jasmine Lorenzini and Arianna Montorsi (TF1 Co-chairs), Pilar Aparicio Martinez and Giuliana Rubbia (TF2 Co-chairs)

INCLUSIVE EXCELLENCE: HOW AND WHY?

Report of the TIER online workshop on June 27, 2025

On June 27, 2025, the CoARA Working Group TIER – Towards an Inclusive Evaluation of Research organised an online workshop open to all CoARA members, to explore how inclusivity and research excellence can go hand in hand, with insights from TIER members, best practices across institutions, and emerging reflections on unconscious bias.

The workshop was conceived with TIER presentations followed by a roundtable discussion featuring chairs of various CoARA Working Groups, to build stronger links between WGs, harmonise activities, and encourage open dialogue among members. It was advertised through CoARA newsletter and [website](#), and resulted well attended, with more than 70 participants from diverse organizations.

TIER Workshop “Inclusive Excellence: How and Why?” 27th June 2025

14:00–16:00 (CET), online at the following link:

<https://fnfn-it.zoom.us/j/81548748257?pwd=TXNnWC91QXRuSXdmaDZkZkpBMkVpZz09>

Agenda

14:00 – 14:40 | Welcome & TIER Presentation

Moderator: Silvia Penati

- ▶ **Inclusive Excellence** (*Luca Falzea, Maura Coniglione, Helene Schiffbaenker*) – 13 min
 - ▶ **Best Practices** (*Jasmine Lorenzini, Ester Cois, Ilmari Jauhiainen*) – 13 min
 - ▶ **Survey on Unconscious Bias** (*Maura Coniglione*) – 13 min
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14:40 – 14:55 | Expert Insight

 Urszula Pawlicka-Deger (Wellcome Trust) – 15 min

Moderator: Silvia Penati

14:55 – 15:05 | Short Break

15:05 – 15:45 | Voices from the Working Groups Q&A

Moderator: Giuliana Rubbia

Each WG answers 2 key questions – 10 minutes per group:

1. **Reforming Academic Career Assessment (ACA)**
 Speaker: Rita Morais
 2. **Responsible Metrics and Indicators (RMI)**
 Speaker: Katarzyna Nawrot
 3. **Early-and-Mid-Career Researchers (EMCRs) – Assessment and Research Culture**
 Speaker: Pil Maria Saugmann
 4. **Improving Practices in the Assessment of Research Proposals**
 Speaker: Yvonne Fors
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15:45 – 16:00 | Q&A & Open Discussion

Highlights

Part 1 – Welcome and TIER presentation

In the first part of the workshop, TIER members illustrated key concepts and drivers of inclusive excellence, best practices across Europe, and survey findings on unconscious bias in research assessment. An expert's insight into this topic concluded this part.

Introduction and TIER presentation. Silvia Penati, Università di Milano-Bicocca, TIER chair, briefly reminded that TIER focuses on biases in research assessment, particularly on *gender bias*, which is well documented in the literature. TIER's main goals are to review the criteria used in research assessment from this perspective and to find a set of useful suggestions for best practices to be implemented and mitigate such biases. The revision of the criteria and procedures of research assessment is inspired by the revision of the concept of "excellence" in science, with science in its broadest meaning; for these reasons, *inclusive excellence* has been chosen as the focus of the workshop.

The poster features a central title "Inclusive Excellence: How and Why?" with the date "Friday June 27 2025 14.00-16:00 CEST" and the workshop link "CoARA WG TIER online workshop: <https://tinyurl.com/4t7x7ah6>". Below the title is "Part I - Welcome, TIER Presentation and Expert Insight". The poster is surrounded by ten circular portraits of speakers, each with their name and affiliation. On the left side, there is a logo of a globe held by two hands and the text "TIER – Towards an Inclusive Evaluation of Research".

Speakers:

- Silvia Penati, Uni Milano-Bicocca, TIER Chair
- Maura Coniglione, Uni Milano-Bicocca, TIER Data Analyst
- Luca Falzea, Scuola Normale Superiore - TIER
- Helene Schifffenbaeker, Joanneum Research, TIER
- Arianna Montorsi, Politecnico di Torino, TIER
- Bonaria Biancu, Uni Milano-Bicocca, TIER Co-Chair
- Jasmine Lorenzini, Swiss National Science Foundation - TIER
- Ester Cois, Università di Cagliari, TIER
- Ilmari Jauhiainen, University of Helsinki, The Federation of Finnish Learned Societies - TIER
- Urzula Pawlicka-Deger, Wellcome Trust

Inclusive Excellence. Luca Falzea, research fellow at Scuola Normale Superiore, Faculty of Political and Social Sciences, Pisa, Italy, started to illustrate the concept of excellence as derived from literature. On the one hand, excellence is seen as a self-explanatory

concept, involving several aspects, such as quality, impact, something going above and beyond, know-how, and something that relates to being better than most. On the other hand, it should be noted that excellence refers to a *question of definitory power* (Cameron Neylon et. al., 2017; Connell, 2019) since someone can define what is excellent and what is not in academia, and what are the indicators to be used to define excellence. Moreover, excellence is a *gendered concept*, tailored around specific characteristics (Van der Brink, Benschop, 2011; O'Connor, Barnard, 2021; Catala, 2024; Lagesen, Suboticki, 2024), usually those of male researchers and excluding some part of the community. There are also tensions between an individual approach and the collective dimension, for example, judging someone excellent because, like Albert Einstein, he is very smart and extraordinary or because he/she does something good for the collectivity he/she is inserted in. All these issues have very practical implications in the evaluation of careers. Therefore, the starting point is that *excellence is not a neutral concept*, it is rooted in society and its biases.

Maura Coniglione, University of Pavia, Department of Mathematics, and University of Milano-Bicocca-TIER, commented on some results from the TIER, which has been distributed to individuals in Research Performing (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), asking for their perceptions about research evaluation. According to the perceptions of nearly 2,000 respondents, researchers are evaluated mostly using quantitative metrics as a proxy for their success; the main metrics are high-impact journal publications, research grants and funding, citation counts (RPO) /H-index (RFO), and the prestige of the publication venue. The parameters that have less impact on evaluating a researcher are, in general: Teaching, Peer Review, Student Mentorship and Training, Outreach activities, open-access venues, and Diversity of publications. Perceptions vary among genders. Regarding the impact of traditional metrics, the h-index is perceived as more impactful by females and others than by males. Regarding recognition and academic prestige, females have attributed more importance to awards, honours, cultural awards, invited lectures, and visiting professorships in how they feel evaluated, unlike males and others. When looking at engagement and mentorship activities, outreach activities are considered less impactful by males compared to other genders. Student mentorship and training hold less weight for males than for females and others.

Helen Schifffenbaecker, sociologist at Joanneum Research, Vienna, Austria, expanded the concept of inclusive excellence to a more concrete level. When talking about inclusive excellence, we should refer to some changing features. We should consider *different life contexts of researchers*, which have implications for careers, research outcomes and

excellence. For example, if you have career breaks and publish less, this does not mean that you are less excellent, nor if you are a researcher living in the Global South dealing with topics that are relevant there, which might be perceived as less relevant by reviewers of the Global North, you are not less excellent. We need to take into account that the way science is done changes. We witness more teamwork and transdisciplinary works, the increase of Artificial Intelligence, the need for more competencies for Open Science, to manage projects and teams, ... therefore we should consider all these aspects. *Inclusive* excellence should: strive for a diverse research workforce (under-served subgroups), diverse reviewers; focus on researchers' potential (not past achievements) and on team work; cover broader activities: mentoring, outreach activities, leadership; cover broader research outcomes: policy advise, citizen involvement, open data; focus on broader impact of research: societal relevance, Inclusive Gender Analysis. Since assessment is performed at three levels: for researchers, research teams and research organizations, we have to look at potential indicators in these three levels. Research content and outcomes are transversal to all these three levels. Some ideas about indicators follow for further discussion.

Best Practices from across Europe. Jasmine Lorenzini, Swiss National Science Foundation, introduced the analysis of case studies performed both in RPOs and RFOs in four countries: Finland, Italy, Switzerland, UK and at EU level, which has been done

capitalizing on the expertise of the group. For each case, data have been collected focusing on what is currently done and what are the best practices.

Ester Cois, sociologist at Università di Cagliari and current president of the national conference of Equality Bodies of Italian universities, highlighted that in many countries the DORA and CoARA declarations have been signed, but that there are a lot of variations when it comes to taking into account career breaks, non-linear careers, and diversity of tasks.

Ilmari Jauhiainen, from the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies, illustrated the recommendations on responsible research evaluation in Finland, already published in 2020, well before the CoARA initiative, drafted by a working group with representatives from all key actors of the Finnish research community. Recommendations contain general principles of researcher evaluation (transparency, integrity, fairness, competence and diversity) and good practices for a) building the evaluation process, b) evaluation process, c) diversity of activities and d) researcher's role in the process, and explanations for these practices. A national steering group of representatives from all key actors of the Finnish research community monitors the implementation. In 2024, 87 % of RPOs had taken the recommendations into consideration in the policy documents of the organization.

Survey findings on unconscious bias in research assessment

TIER Online Workshop, 27/06/2025

Survey on Implicit Bias

How language shapes
perception (also)
in Research

Maura Coniglione, Marc Yeste Oliveras

Maura Coniglione (University of Pavia, Department of Mathematics, and University of Milano-Bicocca-TIER) and Marc Yeste Oliveras (University of Gerona) explored responses to the survey targeted to individuals to detect biases. Their analysis revealed that different ways of phrasing questions can reveal unconscious beliefs, bypass social desirability (i.e., the tendency to say what is socially acceptable), and make deeply rooted stereotypes visible. Positive and negative framing impact on responses, and responses may be affected by gender.

Expert Insight – Urszula Pawlicka-Deger (Wellcome Trust)

Urszula Pawlicka-Deger is a Research Manager at [Wellcome Trust](#), an independent and global charitable foundation based in London, UK. She recalled the main funding schemes of Wellcome - early career awards, career development awards, discovery awards- and their assessment process. She highlighted the composition of the interview panels that provide recommendations for selecting applicants; in particular, targeted percentages of women and minorities are achieved, while other areas need

improvement, e.g. disabled. Regarding the assessment criteria, 50% of the overall assessment score refers to the research proposal, while the remaining is for the applicant 25% and the research environment 25%. She detailed the features for each of all three areas. They invite the committee members to look at narrative CVs, and not the number of publications.

Part 2 – Voices from CoARA Working Groups

The second part of the workshop has been moderated by Giuliana Rubbia, INGV, Italy, TIER Capacity Building and Communication. The representatives of four CoARA working groups shared their evolving perspectives and recommendations, replying to the two questions posed by TIER:

1) How does the notion of excellence in research translate to the specific focus of your working group? What are your working group propositions to challenge/change that?

2) Which links do you see between your work that seeks to redefine these aspects of excellence and the work of the TIER working group devoted to fostering inclusive excellence?

Inclusive Excellence: How and Why?
Friday June 27 2025 14.00-16:00 CEST
CoARA WG TIER online workshop: <https://tinyurl.com/4t7x7ah6>
Part II - Voices from the Working Groups Q&A

TIER – Towards an Inclusive Evaluation of Research

How does the notion of excellence in research translate to the specific focus of your working group? What are your working group propositions to challenge/change that?

Which links do you see between your work that seeks to redefine these aspects of excellence and the work of the TIER working group devoted to fostering inclusive excellence?

 Pii Maria Saugmann EURODOC President Early-and-mid-Career Researchers (EMCRs) - Assessment and Research Culture				
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CoARA WG ACA. Rita Morais, Adviser for Research and Innovation (R&I) at the European University Association (EUA), briefly reported on lessons learned regarding the meaning of reform and expected commonalities with TIER in the Working Group on Reforming Academic Career Assessment (ACA).

According to their [report](#) "Rethinking academic career assessment - Lessons and tools for reform", Rita pointed out that:

- The scope of academic career assessment is expanding, with a shared aim of systematically merit academic staff for a broader scope of academic activities beyond just publications, including teaching, leadership, teamwork, open science, societal outreach...

- The reform requires an open conversation on the nature of quality and excellence. There are diverging views on what ‘excellent research’ or ‘outstanding teaching’ actually mean. There is a need for an inclusive conversation on what excellence entails and how it can best be evaluated and measured.

The [ACA survey](#) “Mapping academic career assessment reform initiatives - survey outcomes” revealed that it is important:

- to offer a more diversified, fair set of evaluation criteria, encompassing multifaceted academic work and considering staff wellbeing
- to ensure that academic career evaluation processes are inclusive and equitable, and that they are not affected by unconscious or structural biases
- to develop processes considering gender equality, diverse committee compositions, and openness to applicants from various backgrounds, since diversity in the committee composition is compulsory to ensure diverse perspectives
- to implement assessment processes that accommodate different career stages, profiles, and interdisciplinary contributions.

For a possible link with TIER, ACA is committed to developing a framework/toolbox on academic career assessment, providing a conceptual organisation of existing practical tools with several thematic dimensions, including one on “Integrating equality, diversity and inclusiveness in ACA processes”, meaning that assessment criteria and procedures actively value and accommodate different backgrounds, career paths and life circumstances, reducing biases.

CoARA WG RMI. Katarzyna Nawrot of the University of Warsaw, representative for the Working Group on Responsible Metrics and Indicators (RMI), illustrated the goals of RMI, which are to explore the current status of indicators and provide recommendations for combining quantitative and qualitative indicators, as one of the core commitments of CoARA. She emphasised that quality and excellence do not exclude the use of quantitative indicators, and that they are attempting to provide a menu or decision tree to support the proper selection of indicators. With RMI, they are looking at complex patterns of indicators which refer to several factors: the purpose of research assessment, the subject or area of research assessment, the subject or unit of research

assessment and the evaluation process, i.e. the nature and tools of assessment. TIER contribution to the Helsinki meeting was inspirational to them, because gender issues and minorities were not initially considered in RMI, but indeed they should be. She proposed to take part in the current [RMI survey](#), which does not include gender bias, but now they intend to consider gender in the subject and object of research assessment.

CoARA WG EMCRs. Pil Maria Saugman, co-chair of the Working Group Early and Mid-Career Researchers - Assessment and Research culture (EMCRs) and current president of European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc), also joined the table. She pointed out that the research sector is shaped by early and mid-career researchers and doctoral education, and that EMCRs should be included in conversations about research assessment, in particular about the assessment practices that regard them. The WG EMCRs are focusing on looking at differences and similarities in the habilitation processes across Europe. They do not specifically examine excellence, but rather are interested in understanding where these notions of excellence emerge and how they are defined, as well as the similarities and differences across Europe. They are interested in looking at TIER work and at synergies with the other WGs from their perspective of the habilitation process, which can serve as an amplifier or a blocker of good practices.

CoARA WG Improving Procedures in the Assessment of Research Proposals. Yvonne Fors, University of Stockholm, presented the WG, where participants are mostly funding bodies and funding organisations, with a task focused on criteria for the selection of the research project and innovative approaches to the review process. The objective of the WG is to screen *review criteria* and *review procedures* for improvement potential regarding the CoARA Commitments 1-3 (i.e. to recognise diversity of contributions, careers and practices, to strengthen qualitative review and to abandon inappropriate uses of quantitative metrics). According to their survey, very few organisations have an official definition of scientific excellence or scientific quality; at the same time, they see a wide field of operationalisations through review criteria, but a loose area of consensus regarding core review criteria. She presented some preliminary results of the survey, showing, for example, how (35) funders reacted to the question regarding the aspects considered important in the assessment of research proposals, or which criteria are considered when making funding decisions. She briefly summarised the content of two discussion papers on Improving alignment with CoARA commitment 1, and Improving alignment with CoARA commitment 2 and 3. Both the report from the survey and the discussion papers are in progress, and they will be finalized after the WG meeting scheduled for September 25, hosted by the Swedish Knowledge Foundation.

Q&A and Open discussion

From the audience, Gabriel Bianchi from the Slovak Academy of Sciences (SAS) appreciated the inspirational presentations. He also expressed the frustration from the perspective of social sciences and humanities (SSH) with technical and natural sciences, which “believe” in scientometrics and “big grant” criteria for excellence, such as ERC grants or publications in the first decile. SSH cannot compete with these quantitative criteria. He reminded one SAS initiative among 25 social scientists who succeeded in identifying nine indicators for alternative excellence, very different from what natural sciences and technical sciences can offer. He would be pleased to exchange further views on this aspect.

Giuliana Rubbia, INGV Italy, TIER Capacity building and communication, commented that various commonalities emerged from the round table, and that this sounds promising. She welcomed Gabriel Bianchi’s suggestion, and stressed that there is room for further dissemination and popularisation events of TIER’s work within CoARA member organisations and National Chapters.

Silvia Penati, TIER chair, expressed her satisfaction with the success of the event; she identified many topics and interests in common, which herald a possible fruitful collaboration among Working Groups, in particular when we will be requested to homogenise the final outputs. She concluded by thanking all participants. Indeed, TIER workshop “Inclusive Excellence: How and Why” represented an opportunity to share insights but also to build stronger links between Working Groups, harmonise activities, and encourage open dialogue among members.

[Slides and registrations are available.](#)

Report drafted by Giuliana Rubbia, TIER TF2 Capacity building and communication.

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